

1 **Validity of the Kinarm Approach-Avoidance Task for Assessing Automatic Tendencies**
2 **Towards Physical Activity and Sedentary Behaviours: A Registered Report**

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16

17 **ABSTRACT**

18 **Background.** Approach-avoidance tendencies have traditionally been assessed using
19 unidimensional reaction times, measured by moving an on-screen manikin towards or away from
20 stimuli using a keyboard, joystick, touchscreen, or mouse. Recently, a bimanual robotic task,
21 referred to as the Kinarm Approach-Avoidance Task (KAAT), has been proposed to provide a
22 continuous, high-resolution, multidirectional, and ecologically relevant assessment of the
23 spatiotemporal dynamics that characterize these tendencies.

24 **Objective.** To assess the construct, concurrent, convergent, and predictive validity of the KAAT
25 with stimuli depicting physical activity and sedentary behaviours.

26 **Methods.** Healthy participants performed the KAAT and the keyboard-based manikin task.
27 Approach-avoidance tendencies were quantified using reaction time, time to peak velocity, x-flips,
28 and opposite displacement. Physical activity was assessed with accelerometers. Additional
29 questionnaires measured intentions, explicit attitudes, automaticity, and the valuation of physical
30 effort. Trial-level approach-avoidance tendencies were analysed using linear mixed-effects
31 models. Concurrent validity between the KAAT and the manikin task and predictive associations
32 with physical activity and related psychological constructs were evaluated using correlations and
33 hierarchical regressions, controlling for age, sex, height, weight, handedness, error rate, and
34 elapsed time.
35

36 **Keywords.** Psychology, Motivation, Robotics, Validation Study, Exercise, Sedentary Behaviour

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, dual-process models have been proposed to explain physical activity behaviour [1–4]. These models suggest that physical activity is shaped by both controlled (also called reflective) processes (e.g., explicit attitudes, intentions, valuation of physical effort) and automatic processes (e.g., automatic affective reactions, approach-avoidance tendencies). Controlled processes are deliberative, resource-intensive, and conscious, whereas automatic processes are fast, effortless, and operate with limited conscious awareness [5]. According to these models, repeated experiences of pleasure or displeasure during physical activity create learned associations that generate automatic affective evaluations when physical activity-related cues are encountered. These evaluations can influence controlled processes and elicit approach or avoidance impulses that affect the likelihood of being physically active. Among automatic processes, approach-avoidance tendencies are thought to be particularly proximal to behaviour, as they reflect automatic action orientations towards or away from environmental stimuli [6–9].

In health psychology, approach-avoidance tendencies have traditionally been assessed using unidimensional reaction times to task-relevant stimuli, measured via interfaces such as a keyboard, joystick, touchscreen, or computer mouse [10–14]. Consistent with this broader literature, physical activity research has primarily assessed approach-avoidance tendencies using the manikin task in which reaction times are measured by moving an on-screen manikin towards (i.e., approach) or away (i.e., avoid) from stimuli depicting physical activity and sedentary behaviours [9,15–32]. By measuring the time required to initiate conceptual (i.e., via keyboard) or actual (e.g., via joystick) approach or avoidance movements in response to stimuli related to physical activity, reaction times provide an indirect measure of the strength and direction of automatically activated tendencies.

Despite their theoretical grounding and widespread use, unidimensional reaction-time measures have limitations. Because reaction times reduce the motor response to a single timepoint, they conflate multiple perceptual, cognitive, and motor processes while discarding kinematic information about movement execution. As a result, they fail to capture the temporal dynamics and spatial characteristics of behaviour, such as trajectory, amplitude, and changes in direction. In addition, constraining responses to a single spatial dimension (e.g., anteroposterior joystick movements) may oversimplify the inherently multidirectional nature of approach-avoidance tendencies and limit sensitivity to how these tendencies are expressed across space.

Other limitations relate to the task implementation. In joystick-based tasks, approach (i.e., pulling) and avoidance (i.e., pushing) are often simulated via stimulus zooming in and out, respectively, which introduces ambiguity because the same response can be interpreted differently. For example, pulling a joystick brings the arm away from the screen and stimulus (i.e., withdrawal), yet it is typically paired with visual stimulus enlargement, which conveys approach. This mismatch may confound the interpretation of reaction-time differences [23]. By relying on symbolic and discretized responses, keyboard-based tasks such as the manikin task avoid this reference-frame ambiguity. However, because these key presses only indirectly reflect bodily action, these tasks lack ecological validity and sensitivity to fine-grained temporal and spatial aspects of movement execution.

Taken together, these limitations highlight the need for paradigms that capture approach-avoidance tendencies as a dynamic and embodied process rather than as a single latency measure constrained to one spatial dimension. To address this need, a bimanual robotic task implemented on the Kinarm platform has been proposed that provides a continuous, high-resolution, multidirectional, and ecologically relevant assessment of the spatiotemporal dynamics that

83 characterize approach-avoidance tendencies [33]. This so-called Kinarm Approach-Avoidance
84 Task (KAAT) records kinematic data from two handles in a two-dimensional virtual environment,
85 enabling the quantification of movement patterns that may reflect approach-avoidance conflicts,
86 movement-related uncertainty, and hesitation beyond what can be assessed with classical
87 reaction-time-based tasks. However, this task has not yet undergone formal psychometric
88 validation. Accordingly, the objective of this study is to evaluate the construct, convergent,
89 concurrent, and predictive validity of the KAAT.

90

91 **Hypotheses**

92 We formulated hypotheses (H) corresponding to each of the four types of validity
93 addressed by our objective (Table 1). Raw bias refers to the absolute tendency to approach or
94 avoid a stimulus, whereas relative bias refers to the relative tendency, which accounts for
95 interindividual differences in generic approach-avoidance tendencies by controlling for responses
96 to neutral stimuli [9]. Approach-avoidance tendencies were derived from these two types of bias,
97 each calculated from the four dependent variables: reaction time, time to peak velocity, x-flips,
98 and opposite displacement.

99

100 *Construct Validity*

101 To assess the structural aspect of construct validity, which examines whether a measure
102 follows expected internal patterns, we compared raw and relative bias scores separately against
103 zero to evaluate whether the measure could detect systematic bias. We hypothesised that, for both
104 physical activity and sedentary stimuli, KAAT-derived raw bias (H1a–h) and relative bias (H1i–
105 p) would significantly differ from zero across all outcome variables (i.e., reaction time, time to
106 peak velocity, x-flips, and opposite displacement).

107 As an additional examination of construct validity, we compared the magnitude of reaction
108 time-based approach-avoidance effects between the KAAT and the manikin task to examine
109 whether KAAT-derived bias behaved as theoretically expected relative to an established task. We
110 hypothesised that raw bias would be larger when assessed with the KAAT than with the manikin
111 task for both physical activity (H1q) and sedentary stimuli (H1r). We formulated analogous
112 hypotheses for relative bias (H1s, H1t).

113

114 *Concurrent Validity*

115 To assess concurrent validity, which examines the extent to which a new measure is
116 associated with an established criterion assessed at the same time [34], we examined associations
117 between raw and relative bias score derived from both tasks. We hypothesised that raw bias would
118 show small positive correlations between tasks for both physical activity (H2a) and sedentary
119 stimuli (H2b), consistent with previous studies showing limited convergence between approach-
120 avoidance tasks [11,35]. We formulated analogous hypotheses for relative bias (H2c, H2d).

121

122 *Convergent Validity*

123 To assess convergent validity, which examines the extent to which a measure is associated
124 with other measures of theoretically related constructs [34], we examined the association between
125 KAAT-derived relative bias and six outcomes and compared them with the corresponding
126 associations obtained using the manikin task. We hypothesised that the relative bias towards
127 physical activity derived from the KAAT would be associated with (H3a) device-based total
128 physical activity, (H3b) device-based moderate-to-vigorous physical activity, (H3c) explicit

129 affective attitudes towards physical activity, (H3d) intentions to be physically active, (H3e)
 130 valuation of physical effort, and (H3f) automaticity towards physical activity. We further
 131 hypothesised that these associations would be stronger for the KAAT than for the manikin task
 132 (H3g–l).

133
 134 *Predictive Validity*

135 To assess predictive validity, which refers to the extent to which a measure predicts
 136 relevant behavioural outcomes [34], we computed the variance in accelerometer-based total
 137 physical activity explained by KAAT-derived and manikin-derived relative bias scores. We
 138 hypothesised that reaction-time-based relative bias towards physical activity stimuli measured
 139 with the KAAT would explain variance in device-based total physical activity (H4a), and that
 140 adding kinematic-based relative biases (i.e., time to peak velocity, x-flips, and opposite
 141 displacement) would explain additional variance (H4b). We further hypothesised that the
 142 reaction-time-based relative bias towards physical activity stimuli measured with the KAAT
 143 would explain more variance than when assessed with the manikin task (H4c).

144
 145 **Table 1.** A priori hypotheses by validity type

Construct Validity (H1)		
<i>Internal Structure</i>		
H1a: KAAT raw bias in RT _{PA} ≠ 0	H1i: KAAT relative bias in RT _{PA} ≠ 0	
H1b: KAAT raw bias in RT _{SED} ≠ 0	H1j: KAAT relative bias in RT _{SED} ≠ 0	
H1c: KAAT raw bias in time to peak velocity _{PA} ≠ 0	H1k: KAAT relative bias in time to peak velocity _{PA} ≠ 0	
H1d: KAAT raw bias in time to peak velocity _{SED} ≠ 0	H1l: KAAT relative bias in time to peak velocity _{SED} ≠ 0	
H1e: KAAT raw bias in x-flip _{PA} ≠ 0	H1m: KAAT relative bias in x-flip _{PA} ≠ 0	
H1f: KAAT raw bias in x-flip _{SED} ≠ 0	H1n: KAAT relative bias in x-flip _{SED} ≠ 0	
H1g: KAAT raw bias in opposite displacement _{PA} ≠ 0	H1o: KAAT relative bias in opposite displacement _{PA} ≠ 0	
H1h: KAAT raw bias in opposite displacement _{SED} ≠ 0	H1p: KAAT relative bias in opposite displacement _{SED} ≠ 0	
<i>Task-level differences in effect magnitude</i>		
H1q: KAAT raw bias in RT _{PA} > Manikin raw bias in RT _{PA}	H1s: KAAT relative bias in RT _{PA} > Manikin relative bias in RT _{PA}	
H1r: KAAT raw bias in RT _{SED} > Manikin raw bias in RT _{SED}	H1t: KAAT relative bias in RT _{SED} > Manikin relative bias in RT _{SED}	
Concurrent Validity (H2)		
H2a: KAAT & Manikin raw bias in RT _{PA} are associated	H2c: KAAT & Manikin relative bias in RT _{PA} are associated	
H2b: KAAT & Manikin raw bias in RT _{SED} are associated	H2d: KAAT & Manikin relative bias in RT _{SED} are associated	
Convergent Validity (H3)		
KAAT relative bias in RT _{PA} is associated with:		
H3a: Device-based total PA	H3c: Explicit attitudes towards PA	H3e: Valuation of physical effort
H3b: Device-based moderate-to-vigorous PA	H3d: Intentions to be PA	H3f: Automaticity towards PA
KAAT relative bias in RT _{PA} is more strongly associated than Manikin relative bias in RT _{PA} with:		
H3g: Device-based total PA	H3i: Explicit attitudes towards PA	H3k: Valuation of physical effort
H3h: Device-based moderate-to-vigorous PA	H3j: Intentions to be PA	H3l: Automaticity towards PA
Predictive Validity (H4)		
H4a: KAAT relative bias in RT _{PA} explains variance in device-based total PA		
H4b: Kinematic-based relative biases _{PA} explain additional variance beyond that accounted for by KAAT relative bias in RT _{PA}		
H4c: Relative bias in RT _{PA} better explains total PA when assessed with the KAAT than with the manikin task		

146 Notes. KAAT = Kinarm approach avoidance task, RT = reaction time, H = hypothesis, PA = physical activity, SED = sedentary behaviour

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 148
 149 **Participants**
 150 Participants were recruited via social media, emails, posters, and word of mouth. Inclusion
 151 criteria were age between 18 and 60 years and the ability to communicate fluently in French or
 152 English. Exclusion criteria included any conditions that could influence our results, such as self-
 153 reported depression, upper or lower limb injury, a history of psychiatric or neurological disorders,

METHODS

154 alcohol or drug abuse, or the use of psychotropic medications or illicit substances that may affect
155 attention or neurological functioning. The study was approved by the University of Ottawa
156 Research Ethics Board (H-01-25-11075). All participants provided informed consent and were not
157 compensated for their participation. Data were collected between April 2025 and February 2026.
158 Although 100% of the data have been collected, no observations, preprocessing, or analyses have
159 been or will be conducted prior to stage 1 in-principle acceptance, which corresponds to Level 3
160 of bias control according to the Peer Community In Registered Report taxonomy.

161

162 **A Priori Power Analysis**

163 *Simulation-Based Power Analysis for Linear Mixed-Effects Models*

164 Our study was powered to detect a two-way interaction effect using Monte-Carlo
165 simulations with the simr package in R [36], which is specifically designed for power estimation
166 in mixed-effects models. Because no directly comparable effect size estimates were available in
167 the literature, we derived the model parameters from an open dataset [37] obtained from a prior
168 study [16] that used the same manikin task structure and stimuli as in our study. The data were
169 processed and analysed using the same procedures planned for the present study. The only
170 difference was that the following linear mixed-effects model was fitted separately for physical
171 activity and sedentary stimuli to estimate the sample size required for each stimulus category:
172 Reaction Time ~ Movement × Stimulus Type + (1 + Movement | Subject) + (1 | Pictogram).
173 Movement reflected the response direction (approach vs. avoidance), whereas Stimulus Type
174 contrasted physical activity with neutral pictograms in one model and sedentary with neutral
175 pictograms in the other. Fixed-effect estimates, random-effect variance components (VarCorr),
176 and residual variance (σ^2) from these pilot models were then used to generate simulated datasets
177 reproducing the planned balanced experimental design for each experimental stimulus category.
178 Statistical power for the Movement × Stimulus Type interaction was estimated using 1,000 Monte-
179 Carlo simulations ($\alpha = .05$; t-test with Satterthwaite-approximated degrees of freedom on the fixed
180 effect), yielding a Monte-Carlo standard error below ~1% for the power values around .90 [38].
181 We computed simulation-based power curves using the powerCurve function. These curves
182 indicated that achieving 90% power required 32 participants for physical activity stimuli and 45
183 participants for sedentary stimuli (Figure 1). We therefore set 45 participants as the minimum
184 required sample size. However, because the simulation-based power analysis relies on variance
185 components and fixed-effect estimates derived from a single prior dataset and thus carries
186 parameter uncertainty [39], recruitment continued until the pre-specified end of data collection in
187 February 2026.

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192 **Figure 1.** Simulation-based power curves for the interaction between Movement
193 (approach vs. avoidance) and Stimulus Type (experimental vs. neutral) for physical
194 activity (A) and sedentary stimuli (B). Note: IC 95% = 95% confidence interval.
195

196 Sensitivity Power Analyses

197 Sensitivity power analyses were conducted using the final sample size ($N = 96$) to estimate
198 the minimum detectable effect size for each hypothesis [39], assuming a two-sided alpha level of
199 .05 and a conventional target power of 80%. By identifying the range of effect sizes that the final
200 sample is adequately powered to detect, these analyses provide context for interpreting both
201 statistically significant and non-significant findings.

202 For H2a–d, the sensitivity power analysis was conducted using G*Power for a bivariate
203 correlation exact test, and indicated a minimum detectable correlation of $|r| = .28$.

204 For H3, we estimated separate linear regression models for each theoretically related
205 outcome variable. We conducted sensitivity power analyses in G*Power (F tests; linear multiple
206 regression: fixed model, R^2 increase) to approximate the minimum detectable regression
207 coefficient (for H3a–f). We did not estimate a minimum detectable coefficient difference (H3g–l),
208 because G*Power cannot provide a reliable effect size for this contrast. As the G*Power
209 framework yield a Cohen's f^2 estimate, we computed the corresponding additional explained
210 variance (ΔR^2) and used it to derive the semi-partial correlation, which is of similar magnitude to
211 the standardised regression coefficient (β) when multicollinearity is limited.

212 For H3a–f, the regression models included eight predictors: age, sex, height, weight,
213 handedness, total number of errors, time on the task, and the KAAT relative bias term, with the
214 latter being the sole predictor of interest. The smallest detectable incremental effect was $f^2 = 0.084$
215 for one tested predictor. This corresponds to approximately $\Delta R^2 = 0.05$ – 0.08 , when assuming
216 plausible full-model R^2 values between 0.10 and 0.40, yielding a detectable semi-partial
217 correlation of approximately $r = 0.23$ – 0.28 . Accordingly, without significant multicollinearity,
218 $|\beta_{KAAT}|$ regression coefficients of this magnitude would be expected to be detectable with adequate
219 statistical power.

220 For H4a–b, similar G*Power sensitivity power analysis parameters used for H3a–f were
221 applied to determine the smallest detectable increments in explained variance (ΔR^2) for the
222 sequential linear regression models. For H4a, both the predictor of interest and the total number of
223 predictors were identical to those in H3a–f, yielding a minimal detectable incremental effect size
224 of $f^2 = 0.084$. For H4b, three predictors (x-flips, opposite displacement, and time to peak velocity)
225 were entered at the final step of the model, resulting in 11 total predictors. The minimum detectable
226 incremental effect size was $f^2 = 0.119$. Expressed in terms of explained variance, these values
227 correspond to detectable increases in ΔR^2 of approximately 5–8% for H4a and 7–11% for H4b.

228 Because testing H4c requires comparing non-nested models using information criteria,
229 standard a priori or sensitivity power analyses based on null-hypothesis significance testing are
230 not applicable.
231

232 Study Procedure

233 Participants performed the KAAT on the Kinarm Endpoint robotic platform and the
234 manikin task on a laptop using Inquisit 6 software (Millisecond Software, 2015). Task order was

235 randomised, with a five-minute rest period between tasks. Questionnaires were administered after
 236 both tasks were completed, and collected information on age, sex, gender, weight, height, explicit
 237 attitudes towards physical activity, intention to be physically active, physical effort valuation,
 238 usual level of physical activity, and automaticity towards physical activity (Figure 2). One
 239 attention-check question was included in the questionnaires (“Please answer “2” to this question
 240 that allows us to verify that you actually read the questions”). At the end of the session, participants
 241 were provided with an ActiGraph wGT3X-BT accelerometer to record their physical activity over
 242 the subsequent 7 days.
 243

244
 245 **Figure 2.** Study timeline. Note: KAAT = Kinarm approach-avoidance task
 246

247 **Approach-Avoidance Tasks**

248 *Kinarm Approach-Avoidance Task (KAAT)*

249 The Kinarm Endpoint robotic platform is equipped with a 2-dimensional augmented reality
 250 display and provides high-resolution kinematic data. In the KAAT, participants stood while
 251 holding the robot’s handles, with each hand represented on the display by a white cursor (Figure
 252 3A).

253 The KAAT began with on-screen instructions illustrating the upcoming condition. To
 254 initiate each block of trials, participants used either hand to place the white cursor into a green
 255 circle located at the centre of the workspace. For each trial, a blue circle then appeared either to
 256 the left or the right side of the display with equal probability. Once the participant placed the white
 257 cursor of the appropriate hand (i.e., blue circle in the left side required the left-hand cursor) into
 258 the blue circle and held it there for 500 to 750 ms, a stimulus target appeared at one of twelve
 259 possible locations positioned 10 cm from the start target and separated by 30-degree increments
 260 (Figure 3B). Simultaneously, a second target consisting of an open white circle appeared at the
 261 opposite location.

262 Participants were instructed that bringing the white cursor to the stimulus target
 263 corresponded to an “approach” response, whereas bringing the cursor to the opposite target
 264 corresponded to an “avoid” response. If neither target was reached within 3,000 ms, a “Too
 265 Slow!” message was displayed for 750 ms and the trial ended. If the participant incorrectly
 266 approached or avoided a target, an “Incorrect!” text was displayed for 750 ms before the trial ended
 267 (Figure 3C) [33]. A demonstration video of the KAAT is available on GitHub [40].

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Manikin Task

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Figure 3. Kinarm Approach-Avoidance Task (KAAT). (A) Experimental setup. (B) Example trial in which a neutral stimulus appears in the west position and the open circle appears at the opposite location. Dashed circles illustrate the possible stimulus locations for visualisation purposes only; they are not visible to participants during the task. (C) Example trial in which the participant is instructed to approach sedentary stimuli and avoid physical activity stimuli. Hands are shown for illustrative purposes only and are not visible to participants during the actual task.

The manikin task was implemented in Inquisit 6 software [9,18,28]. Participants performed the task in a standing position with the laptop in front of them, with one index finger on the “U” key and the other on the “N” key (Figure 4A). Pressing the “U” key moved the avatar upward, whereas pressing the “N” key moved the avatar downward. When the avatar appeared below the stimulus, the “U” key was associated with an approach movement, and the “N” key was associated with an avoidance movement. The opposite mapping applied when the avatar appeared above the stimulus.

The manikin task began with on-screen textual instructions indicating the upcoming condition. Each trial then started with a fixation cross presented at the centre of the screen for a random time ranging from 500 to 750 ms (Figure 4B). An avatar subsequently appeared at either the top or the bottom of the screen for 1000 ms, after which a stimulus was presented at the centre of the screen. Pressing the correct key triggered the onset of the next trial. If a participant pressed the incorrect key (e.g., pressing “U” when “N” was required), an “ERROR” message was displayed for 800 ms and the trial ended. If no key was pressed within seven seconds, a “TOO SLOW” message was displayed for 800 ms before the trial ended. A demonstration video of the manikin task is available on GitHub [40].

Figure 4. Manikin Task. (A) Experimental setup for the manikin task. (B) Example trial of the manikin task in which the participant is instructed to approach physical activity stimuli.

Experimental Conditions

In both the KAAAT and the manikin task, task performance was recorded in two experimental conditions and two neutral conditions (Figure 5). Neutral trials were used to compute relative bias (see *Raw and Relative Automatic Approach-Avoidance Bias* section) [9].

In one experimental condition, participants were instructed to approach pictograms depicting physical activity and to avoid pictograms depicting sedentary behaviour. In the other experimental condition, the mapping was reversed: participants avoided physical activity stimuli and approached sedentary stimuli.

In the neutral conditions, experimental pictograms were replaced by stimuli with geometric shapes (circles or squares) matched in number and size of information to three physical activity pictograms (swimming, hiking, cycling) and three sedentary pictograms (couch, hammock, reading) [9,18,28,33]. In one neutral condition, participants were instructed to approach circles and avoid squares. In the other condition, the mapping was reversed.

One neutral block was administered at the beginning of the task and the other at the end. The two experimental blocks were completed between the neutral blocks. Each block included 48 trials, resulting in a total of 192 trials. Approach-avoidance response mapping was counterbalanced across participants separately for neutral (circles vs. squares) and experimental blocks (physical activity vs. sedentary behaviour). Within each block, pictogram presentation order was randomised across both types of stimuli.

321
322

323 **Figure 5.** Timeline and stimuli used in the manikin task and the Kinarm Approach-
324 Avoidance Task (KAAT). Approach-avoidance mapping was counterbalanced for
325 participants separately for neutral (circles vs. squares) and experimental blocks
326 (physical activity vs. sedentary behaviours). Within each block, pictogram
327 presentation order was randomised across both types of stimuli.
328

328

329 *Reaction Times*

330 Incorrect responses, responses faster than 150 ms, and responses slower than 1,500 ms will
331 be excluded from the analyses. The lower threshold was selected as a trade-off between the
332 retention of valid observations and the exclusion of anticipatory responses [41]. The upper
333 threshold was chosen based on prior work indicating this cut-off yields reliable estimates and
334 maximises sensitivity [10], and was consistent with the range of reaction times observed in the
335 KAAT pilot data [33]. Familiarisation trials (the first 15 trials of the study and the first 3 trials of
336 each subsequent condition) will be removed from the analyses [18].

337 For the manikin task, reaction time was defined as the interval between stimulus onset and
338 the key press. For the KAAT, reaction time was defined as the interval between peripheral target
339 onset and movement initiation, which will be identified kinematically by first detecting the time
340 point at which acceleration exceeds 1,000 mm/s² and then tracing backward to the last time point
341 at which acceleration was above 200 mm/s². This procedure has been shown to provide a reliable
342 and accurate estimate of movement initiation based on kinematic data [42].
343

343

344 *Error Rate*

345 Error rate was defined as the proportion of incorrect or time-out responses relative to the
346 total number of trials, following the same exclusion criteria applied to reaction times. Higher
347 values indicate poorer response accuracy.
348

348

349 *Elapsed Time and Task Order*

350 Elapsed time was defined as the duration between task onset (manikin or KAAT) and trial
351 completion recorded for each trial. Task order (manikin first vs. KAAT first) will also be included
352 as a categorical variable. These variables will account for potential temporal and order-related
353 effects, including fatigue and learning.
354

354

355 *Kinematic Variables*

356 In addition to reaction time, three kinematic outcomes will be computed to capture
357 complementary aspects of movement dynamics and approach-avoidance conflicts [43]: a
358 derivative measure, a complexity measure, and a measure of deviation (Figure 6). When competing

359 approach and avoidance tendencies are concurrently activated during movement execution,
 360 participants may show altered movement dynamics as they resolve the conflict between task
 361 instructions and underlying tendencies. A summary of all dependent variables is provided in
 362 Supplemental Table 1.

363 The derivative measure, time to peak velocity, reflects reluctance to commit to action. It
 364 was defined as the time elapsed from movement onset (i.e., reaction time) to the time point of
 365 maximum movement velocity [44,45] on each correct trial. Longer times to peak velocity indicate
 366 delayed motor commitment.

367 The complexity measure, x-flips, reflects wavering during movement execution. It was
 368 defined as the number of directional changes along the x-axis [45,46] on each correct trial, which
 369 will be computed as the number of sign changes in velocity leading to a displacement greater than
 370 1 mm. A higher number of x-flips indicates greater decision difficulty [47].

371 The deviation measure, opposite displacement, reflects response competition by capturing
 372 the extent to which the movement unfolds in the incorrect direction on each correct trial. Greater
 373 distance indicates greater response competition.
 374

375 **Figure 6. Kinematic Variables.** (A) Example trial from the Kinarm approach-
 376 avoidance task (KAAT) with corresponding kinematic variables shown in panel (B)
 377 time to peak velocity, (C) number of x-flips, and (D) opposite displacement.
 378
 379

380 *Raw and Relative Automatic Approach-Avoidance Bias*

381 For construct and concurrent validity, the raw approach-avoidance bias will be estimated
 382 from the simple effect of Movement in the linear mixed-effects models, representing the Avoid –
 383 Approach contrast within each experimental stimulus category (physical activity or sedentary
 384 behaviour).

385 The relative bias will be estimated using the planned interaction contrasts of the Movement
 386 × Stimulus Type interaction. Specifically, for each experimental stimulus category, the contrast
 387 between avoidance and approach responses will be compared with the corresponding contrast for
 388 neutral stimuli (Equation 1), thereby accounting for a potential generic approach-avoidance
 389 tendency that may vary across participants [9,48]:

390
 391
$$\beta_{\text{Movement} \times \text{Stimulus Type}}$$
 392
$$= (E[RT_{\text{Avoid Experimental}}] - E[RT_{\text{Approach Experimental}}])$$
 393
$$- (E[RT_{\text{Avoid Neutral}}] - E[RT_{\text{Approach Neutral}}])$$
 394 (1)

395 where $E[RT]$ denotes the reaction time estimated by the model.

396 For the assessment of convergent and predictive validity, the relative bias towards physical
 397 activity will be calculated directly at the participant level using median reaction times (Equation
 398 2). This is because mixed-effects models produce participant-specific estimates that are partially
 399 adjusted (or “shrunk”) towards the group average. While this shrinkage improves the stability of the
 400 estimates, it can attenuate (i.e., weaken) observed associations when these model-based estimates
 401 are subsequently used as predictors in separate analyses [49,50].

402
 403
$$\text{Relative Bias}_{\text{Physical Activity}}$$
 404
$$= \left(\text{median } RT_{\text{Avoid Physical Activity}} - \text{median } RT_{\text{Approach Physical Activity}} \right)$$
 405
$$- \left(\text{median } RT_{\text{Avoid Neutral}} - \text{median } RT_{\text{Approach Neutral}} \right)$$
 406 (2)

407 For conciseness, this section focuses on reaction time. However, raw and relative bias scores will
 408 be estimated separately for each kinematic variable. For reaction time, positive scores will indicate
 409 faster approach than avoidance responses to experimental stimuli, reflecting a tendency to
 410 approach rather than avoid. For kinematic variables, positive scores will indicate greater
 411 movement conflict during avoidance than approach trials, likewise reflecting a tendency to
 412 approach.

413
 414 *Reliability of Participant-Level Relative Bias*

415 To evaluate the reliability of the relative approach-avoidance bias at the participant level,
 416 split-half reliability will be estimated using a resampling-based procedure combined with
 417 intraclass correlation coefficients (ICC).

418 For each participant and for each condition (physical activity and sedentary behaviour),
 419 trials will be randomly divided into two non-overlapping halves using stratified sampling to ensure
 420 that each half contains an equal number of observations from each combination of Movement
 421 (approach vs. avoidance) and Stimulus Type (experimental vs. neutral). Approach-avoidance
 422 relative bias score will be computed separately for each half of the data using linear mixed-effects
 423 models or, for median reaction times, using the same difference-of-differences formula described
 424 above, yielding two independent bias estimates per participant for each dependent variable.

425 To reduce dependency on any single arbitrary split and to obtain a more stable estimate of
 426 internal consistency, this procedure will be repeated 500 times using independent random stratified
 427 splits. For each iteration, agreement between the two bias estimates will be quantified using a two-
 428 way random-effects ICC with absolute agreement (ICC[2,1]) [51,52]. ICC values will then be
 429 averaged across iterations, and 95% confidence intervals will be reported to provide a robust
 430 estimate of reliability.

431 Because split-half reliability reflects the consistency of a half-length measure, coefficients
 432 will be adjusted using the Spearman-Brown prophecy formula to estimate reliability of the full-
 433 length task [53]. Higher ICC values will indicate greater within-participant stability and thus

434 greater reliability of the bias measure. Following conventional guidelines, ICC values < .40 will
435 be interpreted as poor, .40–.59 as fair, .60–.74 as good, and $\geq .75$ as excellent reliability [52].

436

437 **Device-Based Level of Physical Activity**

438 *Accelerometer Measurement*

439 Device-based physical activity was assessed using a 3-axis ActiGraph wGT3X-BT
440 accelerometer sampling at 30 Hz. The accelerometer was worn on the right hip using a belt clip
441 and elastic waistband. Participants were instructed to wear the accelerometer for seven consecutive
442 days during all waking hours, for at least 10 hours per day, except during aquatic activities (e.g.,
443 bathing, swimming). They also completed a daily sleep and wear log to support the identification
444 of waking and non-wear periods. A monitoring week was considered valid if it included at least
445 four valid days, including one weekend day [54–56]. Raw accelerometer files will be processed
446 in R using the *GGIR* package [57,58]. Data will be auto-calibrated and summarised using the
447 Euclidean Norm Minus One (ENMO) metric, expressed in milligravity units (mg). Waking wear
448 time and non-wear periods will be identified using the sleep log in combination with the NotWorn
449 and HDCZA algorithms, with non-wear detection based on a period of at least 60 consecutive
450 minutes classified as non-wear by the GGIR algorithm. Physical activity intensity will be classified
451 using adult hip-worn ENMO thresholds: inactivity, < 47.4 mg; light-intensity physical activity,
452 47.4 to < 69.1 mg; moderate-intensity physical activity, 69.1 to < 258.7 mg; and vigorous-intensity
453 physical activity, ≥ 258.7 mg [59,60]. We anticipated that approximately 15% of participants
454 would not provide valid accelerometer data [61]. Participants with insufficient valid accelerometer
455 data or with data showing post-calibration error greater than 0.01 g (10 mg) will be excluded from
456 device-based physical activity analyses [62], and the number and reasons for exclusions will be
457 reported.

458

459 *Total Physical Activity*

460 Total physical activity will be computed to account for light-intensity physical activity, as
461 this intensity has shown measurable health benefits [63] and has been shown to attenuate the
462 association between sedentary time and mortality independently of moderate-to-vigorous physical
463 activity [64]. Moreover, total physical activity volume across all intensities is more strongly
464 associated with mortality reduction than moderate-to-vigorous physical activity alone [65], and
465 has been adopted as a primary outcome in recent large accelerometer-based cohort studies [64,66].

466 Participants' time spent in each intensity category during the week will be averaged across
467 all valid days to estimate average daily physical activity. Each intensity category will then be
468 multiplied by the assigned metabolic equivalent of task (MET) to account for differences in energy
469 expenditure across activity intensities: 2 METs for light physical activity, 4.5 METs for moderate
470 physical activity, and 8 METs for vigorous physical activity [67]. The obtained weighted average
471 values will finally be multiplied by seven to obtain a weekly total expressed in MET-min/week,
472 reflecting weekly total physical activity volume adjusted for intensity. In addition, device-based
473 moderate-to-vigorous physical activity in min/week will be calculated by averaging daily time
474 spent in moderate and vigorous intensity activity and multiplying this value by seven.

475

476 **Questionnaires**

477 *Demographic and Anthropometric Variables*

478 Sex (male, female), age (years), height (cm), weight (kg), and handedness were self-
479 reported.

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Intention to Be Physically Active

Intention to be physically active was assessed with the item: “Over the next 7 days, I intend to do at least 150 minutes of moderate-intensity physical activity; or at least 75 minutes of vigorous intensity physical activity; or an equivalent combination of moderate- and vigorous-intensity physical activity”. Responses were provided on a 7-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (“strongly disagree”) to 7 (“strongly agree”) [9].

Explicit Affective Attitudes Towards Physical Activity

Explicit attitudes towards physical activity were assessed using two bipolar semantic differential items introduced by the stem: “For me, to participate in regular physical activity is ...” [9,68]. Responses were provided on a 7-point Likert scale for the adjective pairs “unpleasant” (1) to “pleasant” (7) and “unenjoyable” (1) to “enjoyable” (7). Scores were computed as the mean of the two items, with higher values indicating more positive affective attitudes towards physical activity.

Automaticity Towards Physical Activity

Automaticity towards physical activity was assessed using the automaticity subscale of the Self-Reported Habit Index and provided information on physical activity habit strength [69,70]. Participants first read the following stem “Overall, the decision to engage in physical activity is something...”. They then indicated their agreement with four statements: “I do automatically”, “I do without having to consciously remember”, “I do without thinking”, and “I start doing before I realize I’m doing it” ($\alpha = .94$). Responses were provided on a 7-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (“Strongly disagree”) to 7 (“Strongly agree”). Scores were computed as the mean of the four items, with higher scores indicating that engaging in physical activity is perceived as more automatic and habitual, whereas lower scores reflect more deliberate processes.

Valuation of Physical Effort

Valuation of physical effort was assessed using the Physical Effort Scale [71,72], an 8-item questionnaire with two dimensions: approach and avoidance of physical effort. Items were rated on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (“I completely disagree”) to 5 (“I completely agree”) and included statements such as “I usually like activities that require physical effort” and “I tend to avoid situations in which I have to exert physical effort”. Scores were computed as the mean of the eight items, with higher scores on the approach dimension reflecting greater positive valuation of physical effort, whereas higher scores on the avoidance dimension reflect stronger tendencies to avoid effort.

Descriptive Analyses

To characterise the sample, we will report means and standard deviations for age, height, weight, moderate-to-vigorous physical activity, total physical activity, intentions, explicit attitudes, automaticity, and the valuation of physical effort. Sex and handedness will be summarised using counts and percentages. Descriptive statistics will also be calculated for reaction times, number of errors, and kinematic variables, stratified by stimulus type and each movement type.

526 **Statistical Analysis**

527 *Construct Validity (H1): Linear Mixed-Effects Models*

528 To test H1, linear mixed-effects models will be fitted in the R software environment [73]
529 using the *lme4* [74] and *lmerTest* packages [75]. The sub-hypotheses of H1 (H1a-H1t; Table 1)
530 will be tested using the following model specification (Equation 3; R formula syntax):

531
532 Dependent Variable ~ Movement * Stimulus Type * Task + Age + Sex +
533 Height * Weight + Handedness + Error Rate + Elapsed Time + Task Order + (3)
534 (1 + Task + Movement * Stimulus Type | Subject) + (1 | Pictogram)
535

536 Movement (approach and avoid) will be deviation-coded (-0.5 and +0.5, respectively) so
537 that the Movement coefficient represents the Avoid – Approach contrast. Stimulus Type (neutral,
538 physical activity and sedentary behaviour) will be entered as a three-level categorical predictor
539 using treatment coding, with neutral stimuli as the reference category. Planned contrasts will
540 therefore compare physical activity and sedentary behaviour stimuli separately against neutral
541 stimuli. Task (manikin and KAAT) will be deviation-coded (-0.5 and +0.5, respectively) so that
542 positive task-related interaction coefficients indicate larger approach-avoidance effects in the
543 KAAT than in the manikin task. Continuous covariates will be standardised (z-scored) prior to
544 analysis to facilitate model convergence and interpretation. Random effects will include intercepts
545 for Subject and Pictogram. For participants, random slopes will be specified for Task and for the
546 Movement × Stimulus Type effect, allowing individual differences in overall task effects and
547 approach-avoidance patterns.

548 In the case of non-convergence or singular fit, model simplification will follow a
549 predefined sequence. First, correlations between random slopes and intercepts will be removed.
550 Second, random slopes associated with higher-order interaction terms will be sequentially
551 removed. As a final step, covariates may be removed, while all primary fixed effects and their
552 interactions will be retained. This predefined simplification strategy aims to balance model
553 complexity with numerical stability and statistical power [76].

554 For the hypotheses testing internal structure focusing on the KAAT, raw approach-
555 avoidance bias (H1a–h) will be tested using the simple effect of Movement (approach vs.
556 avoidance) evaluated at the level of Task = KAAT, and the levels of Stimulus Type = physical
557 activity or sedentary behaviour. KAAT relative approach-avoidance bias (H1i–p) will be tested
558 using the Movement × Stimulus Type interaction, evaluated at Task = KAAT (see section *Raw*
559 *and Relative Automatic Approach-Avoidance Bias*).

560 For the task-level differences in effect magnitude, difference in raw bias between tasks
561 (H1q and H1r) will be tested using planned contrasts comparing the Movement effect between
562 tasks at each experimental stimulus level. Difference in relative bias between tasks (H1s and H1t)
563 will be tested using the Movement × Stimulus Type × Task interaction, which evaluates whether
564 the neutral-corrected bias differs between the KAAT and the manikin task.

565 Models will be estimated using restricted maximum likelihood (REML). Statistical
566 assumptions will be evaluated using residual diagnostics (Q-Q plots and residual-versus-fitted
567 plots). If substantial deviations from normality or homoscedasticity are observed, sensitivity
568 analyses will be conducted using log-transformed reaction times to assess the robustness of the
569 findings. Statistical significance will be evaluated at $\alpha = .05$ using Satterthwaite-approximated
570 degrees of freedom, and effect sizes with 95% confidence intervals will be reported.

571

572 *Concurrent Validity (H2): Bivariate Correlations*

573 To assess concurrent validity (H2), Pearson correlations will be computed between KAAT
574 and manikin indices of raw approach-avoidance bias (H2a and H2b) and relative approach-
575 avoidance bias (H2c and H2d), separately for physical activity and for sedentary stimuli.
576 Correlation coefficients will be reported alongside 95% confidence intervals and corresponding p-
577 values. The significance level will be set at $\alpha = .05$. Given prior evidence of limited convergence
578 and substantial variability between approach-avoidance tasks [11,35], results will be interpreted
579 with primary emphasis on effect size estimates and their precision rather than statistical
580 significance alone.

581

582 *Convergent Validity (H3): Multiple Linear Regressions*

583 Convergent validity will be assessed by examining whether KAAT-derived relative
584 approach-avoidance bias is associated with theoretically related behavioural and motivational
585 indicators measured at the same time point (H3a–f), and whether these associations are stronger
586 than those observed for the manikin task (H3g–l).

587 For H3a–f, separate multiple regressions will be estimated for each outcome variable:
588 device-based total physical activity, device-based moderate-to-vigorous physical activity, explicit
589 affective attitude towards physical activity, intention to be physically active, automaticity towards
590 physical activity, and valuation of physical effort. Each model will include age, sex, height,
591 weight, handedness, error rate, and elapsed time as covariates, with KAAT relative bias as the
592 predictor of interest. The association between KAAT relative bias and each outcome will be
593 evaluated using the standardised regression coefficient (β), its 95% confidence interval, and
594 corresponding *p*-value.

595 For H3g–l, separate multiple regressions will include the same covariates, along with both
596 KAAT relative bias and manikin relative bias. Including both biases in the same model allows
597 estimation of their unique (partial) associations with each outcome while accounting for shared
598 variance. Standardised regression coefficients and 95% confidence intervals will be reported for
599 each task-specific bias. To formally test whether the KAAT relative bias is more strongly
600 associated with each outcome than manikin bias, planned contrasts comparing regression
601 coefficients ($\beta_{\text{KAAT}} - \beta_{\text{manikin}}$) will be conducted within each model. A significant positive contrast
602 will indicate that the KAAT-derived bias explains more variance in the outcome than the manikin-
603 derived bias.

604 All continuous covariates and predictors will be standardised prior to analysis.
605 Multicollinearity will be assessed using variance inflation factors (VIF), with values above 5
606 considered indicative of potentially problematic collinearity. If detected, this will be transparently
607 reported and considered in the interpretation of regression estimates rather than addressed through
608 automatic variable exclusion [77].

609 To control for multiple comparisons within H3a–f and H3g–l [78], the six hypothesis tests
610 in each set will be treated as a single family. *P*-values will be adjusted using the Benjamini-
611 Hochberg False Discovery Rate procedure ($q = .05$) [79,80]. Device-based total physical activity
612 will be specified a priori as the primary outcome within each family and will be evaluated without
613 correction.

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618 *Predictive Validity (H4): Sequential Regressions and Model Comparison*

619 Predictive validity will be evaluated by examining whether KAAT-derived measures explain
620 variance in device-based total physical activity (H4a and H4b) and whether their predictive
621 performance exceeds that of the manikin task (H4c).

622 For H4a and H4b, a multiple linear regression model will be estimated in three sequential
623 steps. *In Step 1*, age, sex, height, weight, handedness, error rate, and elapsed time will be entered as
624 covariates. *In Step 2*, KAAT relative bias for physical activity will be added. *In Step 3*: kinematic
625 variables derived from the KAAT (time to peak velocity, number of x-flips, opposite displacement)
626 will be added.

627 H4a will be evaluated by examining the change in explained variance (ΔR^2) when KAAT
628 relative bias is added at Step 2. A statistically significant increase in ΔR^2 at this step will indicate
629 that KAAT relative bias explains variance in device-based total physical activity beyond
630 covariates. H4b will be evaluated by examining ΔR^2 when the kinematic variables are added at
631 Step 3. A statistically significant increase in ΔR^2 at this step will indicate incremental predictive
632 validity of the kinematic variables beyond relative bias. Changes in explained variance will be
633 tested using F-tests for nested models. Standardised regression coefficients (β), 95% confidence
634 intervals, and ΔR^2 values will be reported. Multicollinearity will be assessed as described for H3.

635 To test H4c, a separate regression including the same covariates as in Step 2 will be
636 estimated, replacing the KAAT-derived relative bias with the manikin-derived relative bias. The
637 predictive performance of the KAAT-based models (Step 2) and the manikin-based model will then
638 be compared. Because these models are not nested, comparisons will rely on adjusted R^2 and
639 information criteria (AIC and BIC) [81,82] rather than F-tests. Lower AIC and BIC values indicate
640 better model fit. Differences in AIC (ΔAIC) will be interpreted using established guidelines [83],
641 with values ≤ 2 indicating similar support for both models, values between 4 and 7 indicating less
642 support for the model with the higher AIC, and values > 10 indicating no support for the model
643 with the higher AIC. Differences in BIC (ΔBIC) will be interpreted using established guidelines
644 [84], with values < 2 indicating negligible evidence, values between 2 and 6 indicating positive
645 evidence, values between 6 and 10 indicating strong evidence, and values > 10 indicating very
646 strong evidence against the model with the higher BIC. In addition, Akaike weights will be
647 computed to quantify the relative support for each model, expressed as a probability-like measure
648 of model plausibility [83,85].

649
650 *Sensitivity Analyses*

651 To evaluate the robustness of the main analyses, sensitivity analyses will be conducted for
652 each reaction-time-based hypothesis using an upper reaction-time exclusion threshold of 3,000 ms
653 instead of 1,500 ms. This threshold has previously been used to accommodate slower responses
654 among older participants [9], and may minimise the risk of influencing results through the
655 exclusion of potentially valid observations [41]. These analyses will assess whether the estimated
656 approach-avoidance bias scores remain robust across alternative reaction-time processing
657 thresholds.

658
659 **Data & Code Accessibility**

660 Supplemental material, data, R scripts, and material used for this study are publicly
661 available on GitHub: https://github.com/Boisgontier-Lab/RR_Validation_KAAT [86].

662
663

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667 the GGIR package.

668
669 **Ethical Statement**

670 The study was approved by University of Ottawa's Research Ethics Boards (H-01-25-
671 11075) and informed consent was collected in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki.

672
673 **Use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and AI-assisted technologies**

674 ChatGPT (OpenAI) and DeepL were used to refine the language, improve readability, and
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676
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685
686 **Competing Interests**

687 Matthieu P. Boisgontier is the founder, representative, and publication director of Peer
688 Community In Health & Movement Sciences (PCI HMS), and serves as a Recommender for PCI
689 Neuroscience and PCI Registered Reports. François Jabouille is a member of the Managing Board
690 of PCI HMS. Kayne Park is a Recommender for PCI HMS.

691
692 **Authors' Contributions**

693 Based on the Contributor Roles Taxonomy (CRediT) [87] individual author contributions
694 to this work will be as follows: François Jabouille: Conceptualisation, Methodology, Investigation,
695 Data Curation, Formal Analysis, Visualisation, Writing – Original Draft, Writing – Review and
696 Editing, Supervision; Timothée Dumas: Data Curation, Visualisation, Writing – Review and
697 Editing; Jérémy Fortier: Investigation; Michaël Patrick Robichaud: Investigation; Brian Nhat
698 Thien Nguyen: Investigation; Frédéric Jolicoeur: Investigation; Silvio Maltagliati: Writing –
699 Review and Editing; Boris Cheval: Writing – Review and Editing; Kayne Park: Methodology,
700 Data Curation, Visualisation, Writing – Review and Editing; Matthieu Boisgontier:
701 Conceptualisation, Methodology, Formal Analysis, Visualisation, Writing – Original Draft,
702 Writing – Review and Editing, Supervision, Project Administration, Funding Acquisition.

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TABLES

Table 2. Study design

Question	Hypotheses	Sampling plan	Analysis plan	Rationale for deciding the sensitivity of the test for confirming or disconfirming the hypothesis	Interpretation given different outcomes
What is the construct validity of the KAAT?	<p>Validity was assessed based on raw bias (difference between avoidance and approach responses in experimental conditions) and relative bias (same difference corrected for the corresponding neutral-stimulus conditions) computed from all dependent variables (reaction time, time to peak velocity, x-flips, and opposite displacement).</p> <p>Hypotheses: - KAAT-derived raw biases would significantly differ from zero for physical activity and sedentary stimuli (H1a-h). - KAAT-derived relative biases would significantly differ from zero for physical activity and sedentary stimuli (H1i-p). - Raw bias would be larger when assessed</p>	<p>The following linear mixed-effects model was fitted separately for physical activity and sedentary stimuli: Reaction Time ~ Movement × Stimulus Type + (1 Movement Subject) + (1 Pictogram), with Movement = approach or avoidance response, and Stimulus Type = physical activity and neutral pictograms, or sedentary and neutral pictograms, depending on the model.</p> <p>Fixed-effect estimates, random-effect variance components (VarCorr), and residual variance (σ^2) from these pilot models were then used to generate simulated datasets reproducing the planned balanced experimental design for each experimental stimulus category.</p> <p>Statistical power for the Movement × Stimulus Type interaction was estimated using 1000</p>	<p>The sub-hypotheses of H1 (H1a-H1t; Table 1) will be tested using the following model specification:</p> <p>Dependent Variable ~ Movement * Stimulus Type * Task + Age + Sex + Height*Weight + Handedness + Error Rate + Elapsed Time + Task Order + (1 + Task + Movement * Stimulus Type Subject) + (1 Pictogram)</p> <p>Movement (approach and avoid) and Task (manikin and KAAT) will be deviation-coded (-0.5 and +0.5, respectively) so that the Movement coefficient represents the Avoid – Approach contrast. Stimulus Type (neutral, physical activity and sedentary behaviour) will be entered as a three-level categorical predictor using treatment coding, with neutral stimuli as the reference category. Planned contrasts will compare physical activity and sedentary behaviour stimuli separately against neutral stimuli. Random effects will include intercepts for Subject and Pictogram. For participants, random slopes will be specified for Task and for the Movement × Stimulus Type effect, allowing individual differences in overall task effects and approach-avoidance patterns.</p> <p>- KAAT raw approach-avoidance bias (H1a-h) will be tested using the simple effect of Movement (approach vs. avoidance) evaluated at the level of Task</p>	<p>- The final sample (N = 96) exceeds the minimum required sample size and is therefore expected to provide adequate sensitivity to detect effects of the two-way interaction.</p> <p>- No simulation was conducted for the three-way interaction comparing tasks (H1q-t) because the KAAT is new and reliable estimates for between-task differences are unavailable. Conclusions regarding task differences will therefore rely particularly on effect-size estimates and 95% confidence intervals.</p>	<p>For all the hypotheses, non-significant effects will be interpreted as insufficient evidence to support the corresponding hypothesis.</p> <p>For each experimental stimulus category: - A significant Simple effect of Movement will be interpreted as evidence of a raw approach-avoidance effect.</p> <p>- A significant Movement × Task interaction will suggest that the magnitude of the raw approach-avoidance bias depends on the type of task used. Specifically, a positive interaction effect will be interpreted as evidence that the KAAT elicits larger approach-avoidance effects than the manikin task. A negative interaction effect will be interpreted as the opposite.</p> <p>- A significant Movement × Stimulus Type interaction will be interpreted as evidence of a relative approach-avoidance effect.</p> <p>- A significant Movement × Stimulus Type × Task interaction will be interpreted as evidence that the magnitude of the relative approach-avoidance bias depends on the type of task used. Specifically, a positive interaction effect will be interpreted as evidence that the KAAT elicits larger approach-avoidance effects, whereas a negative interaction effect will be interpreted as the opposite.</p>

	<p>with the KAAT than with the manikin task for both physical activity (H1q) and sedentary stimuli (H1r).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Relative bias would be larger when assessed with the KAAT than with the manikin task for both physical activity (H1s) and sedentary stimuli (H1t). 	<p>Monte-Carlo simulations ($\alpha = .05$; t-test with Satterthwaite-approximated degrees of freedom on the fixed effect). Simulation-based power curves indicated that achieving 90% power required 32 participants for physical activity stimuli and 45 participants for sedentary stimuli (Figure 1). We therefore set 45 participants as the minimum required sample size.</p>	<p>= KAAT, and the levels of Stimulus Type = physical activity or sedentary behaviour.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - KAAT relative approach-avoidance bias (H1i-p) will be tested using the Movement \times Stimulus Type interaction, evaluated at Task = KAAT. - Difference in raw bias between tasks (H1q and H1r) will be tested using the Movement \times Task interaction, evaluated separately at the physical-activity and sedentary-behaviour levels of experimental stimuli. - Difference in relative bias between tasks (H1s and H1t) will be tested using the Movement \times Stimulus Type \times Task interaction, which evaluates whether the neutral-corrected bias differs between the KAAT and the manikin task. 		
<p>What is the concurrent validity of the KAAT?</p>	<p>Hypotheses:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - raw bias would show small positive correlations between tasks for both physical activity (H2a) and sedentary stimuli (H2b) - relative bias would show small positive correlations between tasks for both physical activity (H2c) and sedentary stimuli (H2d). 		<p>Pearson correlations will be computed between KAAT and manikin indices of raw approach-avoidance bias (H2a and H2b) and relative approach-avoidance bias (H2c and H2d), separately for physical activity and for sedentary stimuli. Correlation coefficients will be reported alongside 95% confidence intervals and corresponding p-values. The significance level will be set at $\alpha = .05$.</p>	<p>For H2a-d, sensitivity power analysis was conducted using G*Power for a bivariate correlation exact test, assuming a two-tailed $\alpha = .05$, 80% power, and a total sample size of $N = 96$, and indicated a minimum detectable correlation of $r = .28$.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Significant positive correlations with a 95% confidence interval entirely above $r = .28$ will be interpreted as support for concurrent validity. - Positive correlations with 95% confidence intervals including $r = .28$, irrespective of statistical significance, will be interpreted as inconclusive with respect to associations of at least this magnitude. - Positive correlations with 95% confidence intervals entirely below $r = .28$, irrespective of statistical significance, will be interpreted as indicating that the data are inconsistent with an association of at least this magnitude. - Significant correlations in the opposite direction will be interpreted as indicating inconsistency between tasks, calling into question their comparability.

<p>What is the convergent validity of the KAAT?</p>	<p>Hypotheses: - relative bias towards physical activity derived from the KAAT would be associated with (H3a) device-based total physical activity, (H3b) device-based moderate-to-vigorous physical activity, (H3c) explicit affective attitudes towards physical activity, (H3d) intentions to be physically active, (H3e) valuation of physical effort, and (H3f) automaticity towards physical activity - these associations would be stronger for the KAAT than for the manikin task (H3g-l).</p>		<p>- For H3a-f, separate multiple regressions will be estimated for each outcome variable. Each model will include 7 covariates (age, sex, height, weight, handedness, error rate, and elapsed time) + the KAAT relative bias as the predictor of interest. - For H3g-l, separate multiple regressions will include the same covariates + the KAAT relative bias + the manikin relative bias. Including both biases in the same model allows estimation of their unique (partial) associations with each outcome while accounting for shared variance. Planned contrasts comparing regression coefficients ($\beta_{KAAT} - \beta_{manikin}$) will be conducted within each model to test whether the KAAT relative bias is more strongly associated with each outcome than manikin bias. - To control for multiple comparisons within H3a-f and H3g-l [78], the six hypothesis tests in each set will be treated as a single family and p-values will be adjusted using the Benjamini-Hochberg False Discovery Rate procedure ($q = .05$) [79,80]. Device-based total physical activity will be specified a priori as the primary outcome within each family and will be evaluated without correction.</p>	<p>We conducted sensitivity power analyses in G*Power (F tests; linear multiple regression: fixed model, R^2 increase, 8 predictors, 1 tested predictor) to approximate the minimum detectable regression coefficient (for H3a-f). The smallest detectable incremental effect was $f^2 = 0.084$. This corresponds to approximately $\Delta R^2 = 0.05-0.08$, when assuming plausible full-model R^2 values between 0.10 and 0.40, yielding a detectable semi-partial correlation of approximately $r = 0.23-0.28$. Without significant multicollinearity, this corresponds approximately to the magnitude of the β_{KAAT} coefficient that the analysis is expected to detect with adequate statistical power. We did not estimate a minimum detectable coefficient difference (H3g-l), because G*Power cannot provide a reliable effect size for this contrast</p>	<p>- A significant standardized coefficient β_{KAAT} with a 95% confidence interval entirely above zero will be interpreted as evidence that the KAAT relative bias is positively associated with the corresponding outcome. A significant negative coefficient with a confidence interval entirely below zero will be interpreted as evidence of an association in the opposite direction. - A significant positive planned contrast will be interpreted as evidence that KAAT relative bias is more strongly associated with the corresponding outcome than manikin relative bias. A significant negative contrast will indicate the opposite. - KAAT coefficients with 95% confidence intervals including effects of approximately $\beta_{KAAT} = .23-.28$, irrespective of statistical significance, will be interpreted as inconclusive with respect to associations of at least this magnitude. - KAAT coefficients with a 95% confidence interval entirely within the lower limits of the minimum detectable effect (e.g., $-.23$ to $+.23$) will be interpreted as indicating that the data are inconsistent with associations of at least this magnitude. - For secondary outcomes, significant level will be adjusted using the Benjamini-Hochberg false discovery rate procedure ($q = .05$).</p>
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<p>What is the predictive validity of the KAAT?</p>	<p>Hypotheses: - reaction-time-based relative bias towards physical activity stimuli measured with the KAAT would explain variance in device-based total physical activity (H4a) - adding kinematic-based relative biases (i.e., time to peak velocity, x-flips, and opposite displacement) to the model will explain additional variance (H4b) - reaction-time-based relative bias towards physical activity stimuli measured with the KAAT would explain more variance than when assessed with the manikin task (H4c).</p>		<p>For H4a and H4b, a multiple linear regression model will be estimated in three sequential steps. Step 1 = covariates. Step 2 = covariates + KAAT relative bias for physical activity. Step 3: covariates + KAAT relative bias + kinematic-derived biases. - H4a and H4b will be evaluated by examining the change in explained variance (ΔR^2) at each step. Changes in explained variance will be tested using F-tests for nested models. Standardized regression coefficients (β), 95% confidence intervals, and ΔR^2 values will be reported. - For H4c, a separate regression including the same covariates as in Step 2 will be estimated, replacing the KAAT-derived relative bias with the manikin-derived relative bias. The predictive performance of the KAAT-based model (Step 2) and the manikin-based model will then be compared. Because these models are not nested, comparisons will rely on adjusted R^2 and information criteria (AIC and BIC) (81,82) rather than F-tests.</p>	<p>For H4a–b, similar sensitivity power analysis parameters used for H3a–f were applied to assess the smallest detectable increments in explained variance (ΔR^2) - For H4a, predictors were identical to those in H3a–f, yielding a minimal detectable incremental effect size of $f^2 = 0.084$. - For H4b, three predictors (x-flips, opposite displacement, and time to peak velocity) were entered at the final step of the model, resulting in 11 total predictors. The minimum detectable incremental effect size was $f^2 = 0.119$. - Expressed in terms of explained variance, these values correspond to detectable increases in ΔR^2 of approximately 5–8% for H4a and 7–11% for H4b. Sensitivity power analysis is not applicable for H4c.</p>	<p>- A significant increase in explained variance (ΔR^2) after the addition of the predictors will be interpreted as evidence of incremental predictive validity. - If the observed results are below the minimum detectable effect size (approximately $\Delta R^2 = 0.05$–0.08 for H4a and $\Delta R^2 = 0.07$–0.11 for H4b, depending on the full-model R^2), this will be interpreted as limited sensitivity and the need for larger replication studies. - For H4c, lower AIC and BIC values for the KAAT-based model will indicate greater relative support for that model. - Lower AIC and BIC values for the manikin-based model will be interpreted as evidence against the hypothesised predictive advantage of the KAAT - Comparable model fit (i.e., ΔAIC or $\Delta BIC < 2$) will be interpreted as suggesting similar predictive validity of both tasks.</p>
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